

SCHOOL CLIMATE OF SELECTED ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN PATIKUL EAST DISTRICT, MBHTE-SULU, PHILIPPINES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12665016>

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to explore the school organizational climate of Patikul East District, MBHTE-Sulu. This further investigated the areas of administrative dimension, teachers' dimension and school dimension. Meanwhile, described survey method was used to describe the different dimensions of school climate. The respondents were the elementary school teachers of the selected schools of the same district. Meanwhile Self-constructed questionnaire extracted from literatures was used. Moreover, Frequency and percentage, mean, t-test for independent sample and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were utilized in the analysis of data. This study that majority of the respondents were female, belonging to 34 years and above; 11-15 years teaching experience; and with bachelor's degree. Likewise, the teachers have strongly agreed the school climate in terms of administrative dimension were conducive; they further strongly agreed that the school climate pertaining to teacher's dimension is characterized with high teacher's morale, good working relationship, highly motivated, and with high spirit of collaboration. And they strongly agreed to that the school climate pertaining to school dimension was characterized by conducive learning environment, have strong link with parents and Local Government Units officials, have a very friendly atmosphere and the like. Moreover, there was no significant difference on teacher's perception on school climate in the areas of administrative dimension, teacher's dimension and school dimension according to the respondent's profile. Finally, significant difference was found in administrator's dimension according to the respondents' length of service..

Keywords: *School Climate, Administrative Dimension, Teachers Dimension, School Dimension, Organizational Climate*

INTRODUCTION

Today, more than ever before, education is considered to be a societal investment and a commodity for consumption. As such, there is much needs for educationists alike to amplify educational outcomes if only compensate the financial resources invested in education (Bergen, 2014; Abdurahman & Omar, 2021; Abdurahman et al, 2024). Besides, the school is the home of educators and learners. In order to realize one's potential, it is important to feel safe and accepted in one's working and learning environment. The climate in a school therefore should be of such a nature that individuals could prosper in all areas of their lives.

Adeogun and Olisaemeka (2011) and Isa et al (2024) define school climate as an aggregate measure of school characteristics such as relationship between parents, teachers, administrators as well as physical facilities on the ground. According to Mariita (2012), Nyamosi (2013) and Balla et al (2024) have as well asserted that school climate factors such as social economic status, parent involvement, attendance, school size teaching-learning resources and interpersonal relationships affect teachers' job satisfaction and this can affect student academic performance.

Many school organizations, however, struggle to cultivate the climate they need to succeed. Hellriegel and Slocum (2006) explain that organizations can take steps to build a more positive climate through: communication, values expectations, norms, policies and rules, programs and leadership which require a rich organizational structure, reward systems, technology, or tasks (Datnow, Hubbard, & Mehan, 2002; Jupakkal et al, 2024).

Further, it is a part of administration in an educational system is to provide working conditions favorable to good teaching and effective learning. Sensible administration provides teachers and pupils with adequate facilities and favorable environment for work. To be operative, school principals need to possess educational leadership. Their role is to motivate their teacher to achieve the aims of the educational enterprise.

Relatively, there has been increasing attention on the relationship between management and employees especially in the academic world for decades now. Attitudes of the employees towards their organization, as a result of their work environment, are important issues in organizational behavior literature. Employee behavior in organizations is a result of their personal characteristics as well as the environment, which they work in. In this regard, organizational climate is an important aspect in order to understand employee's work-related behavior and it has been discussed in organizational behavior literature for decades (Bergren, 2014).

Moreover, this study endeavors to empirically determine the dimensionality of school climate towards organizational performance construct in the context of public elementary education particularly in Patikul East District, Patikul, Sulu. Most Elementary schools in Sulu still follow archaic narrative essay type performance appraisal methods. Hence, it would be interesting to study the perception of elementary school teachers in Patikul District as to their school organizational climate based on three dimensions: administrative dimension, teachers dimension and school dimension.

METHODOLOGY

This section discusses the research methodology of the study which includes the research locale, respondents of the study, data collection, research instrument, and data gathering procedure and statistical techniques and scope and delimitation of the study.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at the selected schools of Patikul District under the supervision of the MBHTE-Sulu. This schools includes Don Jose Godinez Elementary School, Kawmpang Elementary School and Latih elementary School The researchers has decided to choose these schools because she felt that there is much need for the district to improve the school climate if only to promote quality standard. Besides, the result of this study could serve as baselined data for some program interventions of the said district. Additionally, the researchers herself is presently employed in the same district. Hence, it is quite accessible for her to undergo the investigation.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the elementary school teachers who are currently teaching at Patikul East District, MBHTE-Sulu school year 2022-2023. They are distributed as follows:

Table 3.1 : Distribution of respondents according to school

	Patikul East District	Employees
1	Don Jose Godinez elementary School	13
2	Kawmpang Elementary School	10
3	Latih Elementary School	7
	Total	30

Data Collection

After the validation of the instrument, the researchers asked the approval of the graduate school dean, the then Dr. Magna Anisa Hayudini, through the recommendation of her thesis adviser for launching of the study. Then, the researchers secured a written

permission from the District Supervisor of Patikul East District to allow her to conduct the study. Once approved, the researchers to sent the letter to the school principal, attached with the approved permit from the supervisor, informing them for the administration of the questionnaire in their respective schools. The questionnaire was administered in the third week of April 2023 and was retrieved a day after.

Research Instrument

In this study, the researchers used survey-questionnaire to obtain data from the respondents. Questionnaire is simply a set of questions which, when answered properly by the required number of properly selected respondents supplied the necessary information to complete a research study (Calderon & Gonzales, 1993). In this study, the researchers' prepared questionnaire on the school climate of selected schools in Patikul East District. Said Questionnaire has two parts. The first part deals with the respondent's demographic profile; and the second part pertains to the school climate which also composed of three sub categories namely: administrative dimension, teachers' dimension and school dimension.

Statistical Techniques

To analyze the raw data gathered from the investigation, statistical tool is necessary. In this study, the researchers used frequency and percentage, weighted mean, t-test for independent variable, and one-way ANOVA. The frequency and percentage were used to analyzed the profile of the respondents. While, mean was utilized to assessed the school climates in respect to administrative dimension, teachers' dimension and school dimension. In like manner, t-test for independent variables was used to test the significant difference of school climate according to gender; and one-way ANOVA was used to test the difference of school climate according to age, length of service, and educational qualification.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This investigation aims to describe the school organizational climate in Patikul East District. The variables include administrative dimension, teachers' dimension and school dimension. Other dimensions such as technical dimension, human relation dimension and rational goal dimension are not included in this investigation. The respondents of the study are the selected elementary school teachers from three schools in Patikul District namely: Don Jose Godinez Elementary School, Kawmpang Elementary school, Latih Elementary School. Self- constructed questionnaire will be utilized. Meanwhile, time constraint is projected to be the limitation of the study.

RESULTS

This sections discusses the profile of the respondents in the context of gender, age, length of service, and educational qualification. This also tackles the school climate of Patikul East District selected schools, MBHTE, Sulu that include three dimensions: Administrative dimension, teachers' dimension and school dimensions.

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the profile of the elementary school teachers in the selected elementary schools in Patikul East District with respect to their gender, age, length of service and educational qualification. The distribution are as follows: As to gender, the majority (80%) were female; As to age, the majority (73.3%) were 34 years and above; in terms of length of service, the majority (30%) of the respondents have already served 11-15 years in teaching; And as to educational qualification, the majority (60%) have just finished their baccalaureate degree.

Table 1: The profile of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	6	20
Female	24	80
Age		
23 years old below	1	3.3
24-27 Yrs. Old	0	0.0
28- 33 Old	7	23.3
34 years old and above	22	73.3
Length of Service		
5 Yrs. and below	5	16.7
6-10 yrs.	8	26.7
11-15 yrs.	9	30.0
16 years and above	8	26.7
Educational Qualification		
Bachelor's degree	18	60.0
With master's units	7	23.3
With master's degree	5	16.7
With Doctoral units	0	0.0
With Doctoral degree	0	0.0

School Climate

This section discusses the three dimensions of school climate which covers the administrator's dimension, teacher's dimension and school dimension based on the perception of the respondents.

A. School Climate on Administrator's Dimension

Table 2 reveals the administrator's dimension of school climate of Selected Schools in Patikul East District. The overall mean is 3.54 which has a verbal description of Strongly Agree. Meanwhile, the highest individual mean is 3.70; and the lowest individual mean is 3.37.

Table 2 : School climate Administrator's dimension

School climate's Administrators Dimension	mean	
1. The School administrator helps solve any school relevant concern of teachers	3.43	Agree
2. The school administrators helps settle minor differences of teachers and staff	3.60	Strongly Agree
3. The school administrator always arrive at the school early	3.40	Agree
4. The school administrator help solve individual conflict among teachers	3.37	Agree
5. The school administrator helps solve group conflict within the school	3.47	Agree
6. The school administrator sets an example by working hard for himself/herself	3.67	Strongly Agree
7. The school administrator keeps the teachers' be informed of the new DepEd thrusts	3.57	Strongly Agree
8. The school administrator is always speaking at the school functions	3.70	Strongly Agree
9. The principal schedules the teachers' work and activities timely	3.50	Strongly Agree
10. The school administrator treats everyone justly	3.54	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	3.54	Strongly Agree

Legend : 1.00-1.49 = Strongly disagree ; 1.50- 2.49 = Disagree; 2.50-3.49= Agree; 3.50-4.00= Strongly Agree

B. School Climate on Teacher's Dimension

Table 4.3 tackles the school climate based on teachers' Dimension of selected elementary school in Patikul East District. The overall mean is 3.62 which has a verbal description of strongly agree. While the highest individual mean is 3.83 and the lowest mean is 3.57.

Table 3 : School Climate teachers' dimension

School Climate Teachers' Dimension	mean	Verbal Description
1. The morale of the teachers are high	3.83	Strongly Agree
2. Teachers accomplish their work with vigour and enthusiasm	3.74	Strongly Agree
3. Teachers are high satisfied with their working relationship	3.57	Strongly Agree
4. Teachers have a smooth relationship with colleagues and school administrators	3.47	Agree

5. Teachers are willing to share their problems with colleagues and the school administrators	3.37	Agree
6. Teachers are socializing with each other	3.64	Strongly Agree
7. Teachers find works as highly motivating	3.64	Strongly Agree
8. Teachers are highly motivated to perform the tasks	3.57	Strongly Agree
9. Teachers invite other faculty members to their house for any special occasion	3.64	Strongly Agree
10. Teachers are willing to collaborate with colleagues to accomplish certain tasks	3.74	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	3.62	Strongly Agree

Legend : 1.00-1.49 = Strongly disagree ; 1.50- 2.49 = Disagree; 2.50-3.49= Agree; 3.50-4.00= Strongly Agree

C. School Climate on School Dimension

Table 4 exposes the school climate in an area of school dimension as rated by the elementary school teachers of Patikul East District. The overall mean is 3.59 which has a verbal description of strongly agree. The highest individual mean is 3.74 and the lowest is 3.40.

Table 4: School Climate School dimension

School climates' School Dimension	Mean	Verbal Description
1. The school has very conducive environment for teaching and learning	3.50	Strongly Agree
2. The school establishes a strong link with the parents.	3.54	Strongly Agree
3. The school establishes a strong link with other schools.	3.50	Strongly Agree
4. The school has a warmth welcoming environment for its guests.	3.74	Strongly Agree
5. The school establishes a strong link with the Local Government Units officials.	3.40	Agree
6. The school has a very encouraging environment to work	3.47	Agree
7. The school has set a very clear goal for the students.	3.74	Strongly Agree
8. The school has a very democratic environment for everyone.	3.70	Strongly Agree
9. The school has set its own standard for learning	3.74	Strongly Agree
10. The school has a friendly atmosphere for students and parents	3.67	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	3.59	Strongly Agree

Profile and School Climate

This Section presents the significant difference of school climate with the teacher's demographic profile as to gender, age, educational qualification and length of service.

A. School Climate and Gender

Table 5 depicts the significant difference of school climate in terms of administrator's dimension, Teacher's Dimension and School's dimension according to respondent's gender. The following were found: For administrator's dimension, the sig. value is 5.92; As to Teacher's dimension, the sig. value is .883; and as to School's dimension, the sig. value is .922.

Table 5: Significant difference of school climate according to gender.

Group Statistics						
	Gender	N	Mean Diff.	Sig 2-tailed	Decision	Interpretation
Administrator's Dimension	male	6	208	5.92	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
	female	24	208			
Teacher's Dimension	male	6	058	.836	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
	female	24	058			
School's Dimension	male	6	025	.922	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
	female	24	025			

B. School Climate and Length of Service

Table 6 presents the significant difference of school climate in terms of administrator's dimension, Teacher's Dimension and School's dimension according to respondent's length of service. The following were found: For administrator's dimension, the sig. value is .005; As to Teacher's dimension, the sig. value is .017; and as to School's dimension, the sig. value is .118.

Table 6: Significant Difference of School climate according to length of service

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Administrator's Dimension	Between Groups	3.485	3	1.162	5.412	.005

Teacher's Dimension	Within Groups	5.581	26	.215	4.052	.017
	Total	9.067	29			
	Between Groups	1.613	3	.538		
School Dimension	Within Groups	3.450	26	.133	2.150	.118
	Total	5.063	29			
	Between Groups	1.171	3	.390		
	Within Groups	4.719	26	.181		
	Total	5.890	29			

C. School Climate and Educational Qualification

Table depicts the significant difference of school climate in terms of administrator's dimension, Teacher's Dimension and School's dimension according to respondent's gender. The following were found: For administrator's dimension, the sig. value is .071; As to Teacher's dimension, the sig. value is .460; and as to School's dimension, the sig. value is .233.

Table 7: Significant Difference of School climate according to educational qualification

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Administrator's Dimension	Between Groups	1.613	2	.807	2.922	.071
	Within Groups	7.453	27	.276		
	Total	9.067	29			
Teacher's Dimension	Between Groups	.283	2	.142	.800	.460
	Within Groups	4.780	27	.177		
	Total	5.063	29			
School Dimension	Between Groups	.603	2	.301	1.540	.233
	Within Groups	5.287	27	.196		
	Total	5.890	29			

DISCUSSION

This section discusses the profile of the respondents; the school climate of selected schools of Patikul East District, MBHTE-Sulu according to administrative dimensions, teachers' dimension and school dimension.

A. Profile of the Respondents

Based from table 1, of the 30 teacher respondents from the selected elementary school of Patikul East District, the majority 24 (80 %) were female and only 6 (20%) were male. This indicates the female teachers remain dominant in the educational playing field.

As to respondents' age, the majority 22 (73.3%) were 34 years and above; while 7 (23.3%) were at the age bracket of 28-33 years old; and only one (3.3%) is belonging to 23 years old and below. The data pointed out that majority of the elementary school teachers in Patikul East District are at the middle age already and about to reach the peak of their career. This suggests that there is a need for the MBHTE-Sulu to hire more younger faculty members to carry out the most complex teaching responsibilities.

As to their length of service, the majority nine (30%) of the respondents are already in the service from 11-15 years; while eight (26.7%) are serving 6-10 years and other eight (26.7%) have rendered the same; and only five (16.7%) have been serving five years and below. Meanwhile, in terms of their educational qualification, 18 (60%) of the faculty members have finished their bachelor's degree; while seven (23.3%) of them have their master's units; and only five (16.7%) have already finished their masteral degree. This data clearly suggests that there is an urgent need for the faculty members to upgrade themselves through professional advancement if only to cope with the current explosion of information and technology in the landscape of education.

B. School Climate's Administrative Dimension

Gleaning from Table 2, as attested by an overall mean of 3.54 which has a verbal description of strongly agree, this indicates that the elementary school teachers of selected elementary schools in Patikul East District have strongly agreed that their school administrators have performed the administrative responsibilities emanates from their position as reflected in the same table. This means the school climate pertaining to administrative dimension is relatively very conducive.

When it is taken individually, the teachers have strongly agreed (mean=3.70) that the school administrators are always speaking at the school functions; that they set an example by working hard for themselves (mean=3.67); and they too help settle minor differences of teachers and staff (mean=3.67). Further, the respondents have strongly agreed (mean=3.57) that their school administrators have kept the teachers informed of the new DepEd thrusts; treats everyone justly (mean=3.54; and schedules the teachers' work and activities timely (mean=3.50).

On the other hand, the respondents agreed (mean=3.47) that their school administrators help them solve group conflict within the school; help solve any school relevant concern of teachers (m=3.43); always arrive at the school early (m=3.40); and they always help solve individual conflict among teachers (mean=3.370).

Corollary, effective leaders must ensure continuity in the school instructional program (Leithwood & Riehl, 2003) and must spend time to monitor instructional programs, curriculum implementation, and the quality of instructional practices (Fink & Resnick, 2001). Hoy, Sabo, & Barnes, (1996) and Abu-Saad & Hendrix, (1995) affirmed that the principal is the single most important individual in the development of a school's climate. In schools, therefore, school administrators can become effective change agents who are responsible for creating change and healthy school climate (Abdurahman N., Abdurahman N., et al.,2024).

In the same vein, Several quantitative studies (Hallinger & Heck, 1998; Hoy, Tarter, & Bliss, 1990; Kelley, Thornton, & Daughtery, 2005) have confirmed that school principals have the potential to the climate within the school building. A smoothly functioning school requires a leader's focused time and effort to effectuate change in the school setting. More than anything else, the school must first be a safe and has a positive learning environment for all. School leaders are charged to ensure this (Cotton, 2003). Schools showing academic improvement are more likely to have strong organizational managers who amplified their creativity and innovation in the workplace(Horng & Loeb, 2010; Danielson, 2002).

C. School Climate's Teachers Dimension

Gleaning from Table 3, with an overall mean of 3.62 which has a verbal description of strongly agree, this indicates that the elementary school teachers of selected elementary schools in Patikul East District have strongly agreed that the school climate pertaining to teacher's dimension is characterized with high teacher's morale, good working relationship , highly motivated, and with high spirit of collaboration and the like.

When taking singly, the teachers have strongly agreed (mean=3.87) that their morale is high; that they have accomplish their work with vigor and enthusiasm (mean=3.74); and that they are willing to collaborate with colleagues to accomplish certain tasks (mean=3.74); likewise, they strongly agreed (mean=3.64) that teachers are socializing with each other; find their works motivating; and even inviting each other to their own house. More so, teachers have strongly agreed (mean= 3.57) that they are highly satisfied with their working relationship and highly motivated to perform their own tasks.

Anent this findings, Farrant (1980) contends that the professional skills of the teachers establish a productive classroom atmosphere through a carefully planned teaching structures. He further asserts that professional competence often transforms into high quality of teaching that has consequential impact on the learning of the pupils. Also in Asanji et al (2024) in their study on Job Satisfaction of Teachers in selected

elementary school in Pangutaran District that if teachers morale is high, they are highly motivated to perform their daily tasks which thereby contributed much to their inner satisfaction in the workplace.

Meanwhile, researchers such as Goldhaber (2002), Greenwald, Hedges, and Laine (1996), Nye, Konstantopoulos, and Hedges (2004), Wenglinsky (2001), and Wilson and Floden (2003) however, found credentials such as graduate degrees to be weakly related to teacher performance, during their first and second year of their teaching career. Agyeman (1993) and Abdurahman (2024) reported that teachers, lacking of both the academic and the professional teacher qualification, would undoubtedly have a negative influence on the teaching and learning of the students. However, he further stated that a teacher who is academically and professionally qualified, but works under unfavorable conditions would be less dedicated to his work and thus be less productive in the work place than a teacher who is unqualified but works under favorable school climate.

D. School Climate's School Dimension

As exposed in Table 4, the elementary school teachers have strongly agreed, with an overall mean of 3.59, that the school climate under school dimensions have conducive learning environment, have strong link with parents and Local Government Units officials, have a very friendly atmosphere and the like.

Specifically, the teachers have strongly agreed (mean=3.74) that the school has a warmth welcoming environment for its guests ; has set a very clear goal for the students ; and has set its own standard for learning; They too strongly agreed (mean = 3.70) that the school has a very democratic environment for everyone; has a friendly atmosphere for students and parents (mean=3.67); and has establishes a strong link with the parents (mean 3.54). meanwhile, the teachers have also strong agreed (mean = 3.50) that the school has very conducive environment for teaching and learning and has establishes a strong link with other schools. Moreover, they further agreed (mean=3.47) that the school has a very encouraging environment to work; and ha establishes a strong link with the Local Government Units officials (mean=3.40).

Relative to the findings, Kuperminc et al. (1997) and Abdurahman and Abdurahman et al. (2024) observed that a positive school climate can yield best educational outcomes for students and personnel; whereas a negative climate can hinder optimal learning and development. Hence, it can be stated that school climate, if possible can provide an enriching environment, both for personal growth and academic success. According to Cohen et al. (2009) that Effective school improvement efforts involve the students, parents, and guardians, school personnel, and community leaders .

Meanwhile, a school environment or climate may indicate a great deal of cooperation among the various groups in the school setting while another might reveal a climate of tension, friction and even lack of cooperation among the groups. That is to say that the school climate of school could influence the performance of both teachers and

students positively or negatively as the case might be (Facunle & Ale, 2018). Moreover, Leithwood & Riehl, (2003) stated that principals of high achieving schools are clear about the school's vision and goals . While, Kearney & Harrington (2010) affirmed that school leaders must buy-in to both the vision and the learning goals and they must further seek commitment from the various stakeholders where the school is operated.

E. School Climate and Gender

Based on Table 5, there was no significant difference could be found in school climate in terms of administrator's dimension with the corresponding sig. value of 5.92; teacher's dimension with sig. value of .836; and school dimension with sig. value of .922 when grouped according to gender. All the sig. values were above the .05 alpha level and found to be insignificant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which state that " There is no significant difference of school climate according to age: was accepted. This means the perception of male and female teachers on the school climate as to administrator's dimension, teacher's dimension and school's dimension is almost the same.

F. School Climate and Length of Service

Gleaning from the Table 6, there was significant difference could be found in school climate in terms of administrator's dimension with respect to length of service as seen in the corresponding sig. value of .005 which is below the 0.05 alpha level; Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. While there was no significant difference found on teacher's dimension with sig. value of .817; and school's dimension with sig. value of .118 which are above the 0.05 alpha level and the null hypothesis was accepted. This finding demonstrates that there exists a difference on the perception of the respondents in the area of administrative dimension. This means that the performance of the administrators with more than 10 years in service is better than those who were only serving five years and below.

G. School Climate and Educational Qualification

Based on Table 7, there was no significant difference could be found in school climate in terms of administrator's dimension with the corresponding sig. value of 0.71; teacher's dimension with sig. value of .460; and school dimension with sig. value of .233 when grouped according to educational qualification. All the sig. values were above the .05 alpha level and found to be insignificant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which state that "There is significant difference of school climate according to educational qualification was accepted. This means that regardless of educational qualification, the perception of the teachers on the school climate as to administrator's dimension, teacher's dimension and school's dimension is almost the same. This further implies that whether the administrator is a doctoral holder, master' s holder of a mere bachelor's degree holder, their performance as to managing the school climate do not vary significantly.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Throughout the conduct of this study, the researchers have always safeguard the respondents' right to privacy and confidentiality in the pursuit of gathering the data of this investigation. Firstly, the researchers have sent a letter to the respondents that clearly explains the study's objectives, procedures, potential risks and benefits of the study. Teacher-respondents were also informed of their rights to-and-not to participate in the investigation. In respect to the privacy of the participants, data collection occurred in a private place and collected data were secured in an archive to ensure that no individual can access except the researchers themselves. Likewise, all participants were treated with high respect regardless of their different views and opinions. Moreover, the researchers created a comfortable space for the respondents to give them the freedom to express their free will during the course of the investigation.

Acknowledgements

The researchers wish to express their profound gratitude to those, who in one way or the others, who have immensely contributed to the success of this educational undertakings. To the Chancellor of the Mindanao State University-Sulu for his moral supports, encouragement and motivation that boost the morale of the researchers in accomplishing this laudable works. Likewise, to the faculty respondents of Patikul District for their voluntary participation that paved way for the completion of this investigation. Above all, to the Almighty Allah for showering the researches His strengths, guidance and mercy. Without His blessings, this humble works would not have been made possible.

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